

Nuclear Organization of *Motacilla flava*

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Birds are characterized by fluff, flight, a petite genome and a distinctive karyotype. Despite large numbers of chromosomes, the diploid count ($2n=80$) is amazingly constant with $2n = 74-86$ in 63%, $2n = 66-74$ in 24% and $2n = 40$ & $2n = 142$ in the remaining 13% of birds.

The Yellow Wagtail, *Motacilla flava*, is a small passerine bird of the wagtail family Motacillidae, which includes pipits and long claws. This insectivorous bird inhabits open country near water such as wet meadows. It nests in tussocks, laying 4-8 speckled eggs. It is a slender 15–16 cm long bird with characteristic long, constantly wagging tail. The breeding adult male is basically olive above and yellow below. The heads of breeding males come in a variety of colours and patterns depending on subspecies.

Two males and one female specimens of the yellow wagtail were traced in nature. Blood cells were drawn from the *vena basilica* at the point where it crosses radius and ulna. Sometimes in long-legged species, it was obtained from the *vena sphanea* approximately midway the tarso-metatarsus. Approximately 0.1 ml of a sterile solution of Na-heparin (5000 I.U./ml) was drained into a disposable syringe and 0.5 to 2.0 ml of blood sample was drawn. Small syringes (up to 2 ml) were preferred since the vacuum produced by larger syringes causes the *vena basilica* to collapse during suck up. The syringe was shaken to blend the blood cells and heparin thoroughly. The cell plates were prepared after Garg^[2-6]; Garg & Garg^[1]^[7-16]; Garg, Garg & Jain^[17]^[18], Garg & Shrivastava^[19-27] and Garg, Bharadwaj & Garg^[28].

Of some thirteen-plus metaphase plates examined, nine cells had 40 pairs of chromosomes ($2n=80$), although in rest of the cells, the diploid chromosome count varied from 78 to 85. There was no morphological ambiguity between macro- and micro- chromosomes. Macrochromosomes were divisible into two groups :

Group I was represented by three large metacentric chromosomes. It was the largest element of the karyotype ($L^R = 9.54\%$ and $I^C = 44.82$). Group II comprised

five pairs of large ($\geq 7.5\%$ of TML) to medium ($\geq 2.5\%$ of TML) sized sub-median chromosomes (chromosome 4-8). Z-W were fourth in order of size, both sub-metacentric. The last three pairs were difficult to be individualized owing to a regular fall in size, comparable morphology and overlapping array of centromeric indices.

Apart from these eight pairs, there were sixty four small dot-shaped telocentric elements (n=32), scattered hither and thither in the cell plates, amounted to 24.11% of the total genome.

Key words : Cell plates, Chromosomes, Cytology, Genetics, Nucleus, *Motacilla flava*.

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